

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth system

Instrument deployment through Fimbul Ice Shelf borehole

Milestone MS4

OCEAN:ICE is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation
<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

Document Information: Milestone Report

Work Package	WP2 Cryosphere-ocean interaction, processes and feedbacks
Milestone no. & title	MS4 Instrument deployment through Fimbul Ice Shelf borehole
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Review	PP1 - Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI): Chiara Bearzotti
Version	Final
Due date	31 December 2023
Delivery date	30 November 2023

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Means of Verification of the Achievement of the Milestone

This milestone report has been checked by the WP2 leaders.

Partner in charge of delivery of the milestone: UKRI-BAS.

Work Performed

Task 2.4 “Observing the ocean beneath the sea ice fasten to grounded icebergs” is to deploy oceanographic instrumentation into the water column beneath Fimbul Ice Shelf, with the aim of studying the interaction between the base of the ice shelf and the ocean. This is to be achieved by observing in detail processes within the ocean boundary layer – the upper few metres of the water column. The 2023-24 Antarctic season has recently started and will be closed by February 2024. The activities described in this milestone have been planned and are implemented at the time of writing of this short report. An update of this report will be provided at the end of the Antarctic season.

The site selected for this work is M2 (see map). This is a location that has been monitored from several years by an oceanographic mooring maintained by the Norsk Polarinstitutt (NPI). During the 2023-24 Antarctic field season –currently ongoing- NPI plan to reinstate that mooring, and the OCEAN:ICE component will be added at the same time. At M2, the ice is about 400 m thick, and is underlain by a 630-m thick water column. The site is in an area characterised by basal channels, providing added interest to the observations.

Figure 1: M2 location on the map indicates the site selected for the work described in this milestone.

The OCEAN:ICE instruments to be installed consist of a string of temperature sensors, positioned to straddle the deepest part of the ice shelf, and the boundary layer itself. This will be deployed in one

hot-water drilled hole. A high speed (5Hz) acoustic travel time current, 3D current meter will be deployed through another borehole, drilled nearby, to provide turbulence data from the boundary layer. These data will be supplemented by a high speed conductivity-temperature sensor that will allow vertical heat and salt fluxes to be determined using the eddy covariance method.

Figure 2: OCEAN:ICE instruments to be installed.

This task will also make short term deployments of a novel instrument: a Subsea Water Isotope Sensor (SWIS). This instrument will, for the first time, allow in situ measurements of stable isotopes, a key tracer of glacial meltwater.

The OCEAN:ICE project benefits from contextual datasets generated by the NPI activities. These include full water column mooring data, and time series of melt rates supplied by a downward-looking radar (ApRES) installed on the snow surface.

The work performed to date for this task is listed below.

1. All ocean instruments have been procured;
2. The SWIS has been assembled and tested;
3. The data loggers to be used to record the data streams have been assembled, and the necessary firmware written and tested;
4. All equipment has been shipped to Troll Station, the starting point for the field activities;
5. All personnel on station as of 20th November 2023. The tractor traverse is due to depart Troll on 21st November 2023.

Figure 3: Borehole-deployable SWIS instrument. Enclosure above, instrument below.